

Community of Inquiry & Cognitive Load

Influence on Persistence, Performance and Perspectives in online STEM Courses

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Research Team

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Brief Description: The goal of this project was to target key persistence factors through building community in online undergraduate STEM classrooms by promoting Community of Inquiry in asynchronous online discussions while mitigating extraneous cognitive load through both course design and instructor professional development.

Research Objectives:

1. Increase STEM course persistence
2. Increase performance in online STEM courses
3. Positively influence STEM attitudes
4. Decrease extraneous cognitive load
5. Improve Community of Inquiry presences

Key Findings

- Instructor and course design are important for online STEM course persistence.
- Highest cognitive load in asynchronous online discussions in online STEM courses occur with understanding expectations and crafting the initial post.
- Student social and cognitive presences vary throughout a course but are consistent across sections; teaching presence significantly varies; Course design and professional development efforts may improve COI.
- Top-level analysis suggests intervention was successful at increasing social presence of students and teachers while also showing social presence as consistent between direct and indirect measures.
- A structural model between Community of Inquiry presences, cognitive load, and performance in asynchronous online discussions was validated.
- Opt-in of optional faculty PD was low, even with cash incentive.
- The Framework improved Community of Inquiry social presence (direct and indirect measures) and improved cognitive load (reduced extraneous load and increased germane load).
- The Framework improved persistence but did not increase pass rate.
- The Framework increased STEM beliefs (control and normative), leading to increased STEM intention, with an overall increase in STEM attitudes.

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Online STEM Course Persistence

We needed to understand primary withdrawal reasons in online STEM as a baseline so we could understand the influence of the intervention, aimed at institutional characteristics of course design and instructor characteristics.

- Average withdrawal rate of 3.41%, low compared to research literature.
- No difference across STEM disciplines or Gen Ed vs. degree support.
- Introduction to Computing for Engineers warrants investigation as a gateway course.
- External and environmental factors accounted for 49% of all withdrawals while institutional characteristics accounted for 23% of withdrawals. Within external factors, professional and personal conflicts predominated. Within institutional characteristics, course design and instructor predominated.

Challenges

- Initial data reports did not contain robust withdrawal reasons
- Efforts to change the form used by the advisors when executing a withdrawal were unsuccessful due to administrative hurdles
- Training of advisors reduced un-codable withdrawals to under 25%, but there is continued notable data loss

Falconer, E., Wood, B., Branton, A., & Chuaunsu, M. (2023) Why students withdraw from online STEM courses. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education* [Manuscript in press]

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Measuring Cognitive Load in Asynchronous Online Discussions

We applied the NASA-TLX instrument to measuring cognitive load in asynchronous online discussions and validated the instrument through confirmatory factor analysis. This provided us a solid understanding of where students were experiencing extraneous cognitive load so that we could design our intervention appropriately.

- The validated instrument contains four subscales for five discrete tasks.
- Highest cognitive load occurs with the tasks of understanding expectations and crafting the initial post.
- Lowest cognitive load occurs in applying instructor feedback to future work.
- Frustration is a consistently low subscale for all tasks.

	Mental Demand	Temporal Demand	Effort	Frustration
Understanding what is expected	-0.169	-0.170	-0.253	-0.119
Crafting initial post	-0.263	-0.226	-0.164	-0.111
Critically reading posts	0.159	0.112	0.157	0.079
Creating reply posts	0.052	0.058	0.045	0.001
Integrating instructor feedback	0.221	0.227	0.215	0.149

A negative instructional efficiency suggests extraneous cognitive load is higher for this item compared to others

Challenges

- Low response rate reduced generalizability to population due to nonresponse error; need for replication with larger sample size
- Results indicate all modules in a sample must be analyzed for direct measures

Faulconer, E., Bolch, C., & Wood, B. (2022) Cognitive load in asynchronous discussions of an online undergraduate STEM. *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching & Learning*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRIT-02-2022-0010>

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Direct Measurement of Community of Inquiry

To streamline data collection efforts, the methodology for direct measures of community of inquiry presences needed to be established.

- Student social presence and cognitive presence are not consistent throughout a course but are consistent across sections in a term.
- Teaching presence is highly variable in a term and across sections.
- Students tend to demonstrate the lower levels of cognitive presence, confirming previous literature (figure below).
- Provides support for targeted improvements to the course design and instructor professional development to promote community of inquiry.

Challenges

- Anonymous data prevented analysis of impact at the learner level
- Nonresponse error limited generalizability to population
- Python script drafted to aid in data cleaning

Falconer, E., Chamberlain, D., & Wood, B. (2022) A case study of Community of Inquiry presences and cognitive load in asynchronous online STEM courses. *Online Learning Journal*, 26(3), 46-71.

<https://olj.onlinelearningconsortium.org/index.php/olj/article/view/3386>

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Comparing Direct and Indirect Measures of Col in Discussions

Direct measures of Community of Inquiry is time consuming to collect, clean, and analyze. For this reason, indirect measures are often reported in the research literature. However, with emerging machine learning technologies, the use of direct measures is becoming less time intensive. It is not yet known how well direct and indirect Col measures align with each other.

In survey responses, post-intervention students' responses suggested no change in Teaching Presence (p -value=0.914), increase in Social Presence (p -value=0.096), and potential increase in Cognitive Presence (p -value=0.206). In discussion posts, post-intervention instructors' presence densities decreased by 18% (teaching) and increased by 26% (social). Post-intervention students' presence densities increased by 43% (social) and 8% (cognitive).

Top-level analysis suggests the intervention was successful at increasing social presence of students and teachers while also showing social presence as consistent between direct and indirect measures.

Challenges

- Survey did not identify differences between instructor's teaching and social presence, which may have led survey not aligning to direct measures.
- Survey may be overrepresenting active students due to selection bias.

Chamberlain, D., Faulconer, E., & Wood, B. (2024). Comparing direct and indirect measures of social, cognitive, and teaching presence in asynchronous online discussions. [Manuscript in progress]

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Modeling Col, Cognitive Load, & Performance

While some studies have explored relationships between Community of Inquiry presences and outcomes, these relationships have not undergone robust modeling. Statistical covariance model combining both constructs allows us to more effectively design and evaluate interventions.

- SEM model of Col with intermediate latent factors validates survey instrument by Garrison et al. (1999).
- SEM model of cognitive load validated CFA by Faulconer et al. (2022).
- SEM Model for Col-CL Framework revealed statistically significant evidence that total Col presence, Cognitive Load, and grades mildly covary.
 - Teaching presence did not covary with total Col nor grades and low negative covariance with cognitive load (not aligned with literature (Ice et al., 2011; Lee, 2014; Silva, 2018; Zhu, 2018)).
 - Cognitive presence showed a mild negative covariance with cognitive load and mild positive covariance with grades, as expected from the literature (Jo et al., 2017; Stachel et al., 2013).
 - Social presence showed a mild positive covariance with cognitive load and mild negative covariance with grades, deviating with results from the literature (Hostetter, 2013).
 - The overall Community of Inquiry presence, as perceived by the student, negatively covaries with cognitive load (e.g., as Col presence increases, cognitive load decreases).
 - Combined, these results confirm that presence can both increase some cognitive load (germane) while decreasing other cognitive load (extraneous), and that Col presences covary in complex ways with cognitive load and student performance.
 - Teaching presence was the only presence that did not covary with student performance, suggesting efficacy of active learning (where students are the center of the learning experience) as their social and cognitive presences more closely relate to outcomes than the instructor's interventions.

Chamberlain, D. & Faulconer, E. (2024) *Influence of cognitive load and community of inquiry on persistence and performance in asynchronous discussions in online courses*. [Manuscript under review]

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Modeling Col, Cognitive Load, & Performance

Reduced SEM model

(treating intermediate latent factors as measurable values using model estimates)

Challenges

- Data from student perceptions and not direct measures.
- Data collected from two introductory-level STEM courses (Physics and Mathematics) may not be representative.
- Large number of latent factors reduces statistical measure of variance.

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Faculty Professional Development

The faculty teaching the target courses were offered an asynchronous professional development opportunity which mirrored the students' online learning environment for discussions in order to foster empathy for students. The PD was grounded in best practices for reducing cognitive load and promoting student's social and cognitive presence.

- 48% of invited faculty (n=27) participated.
- 8 targeted peer observations gained.
- Feedback from participants:
 - "I wasn't exactly sure what to expect with the peer review, so this was an excellent experience."
 - "It has been interesting to hear the viewpoints of other faculty members teaching online for ERAU. "
 - "Being engaged in this activity puts us into the proper mindset as our students in that for the most part they are working at their jobs while learning new material and we get a better appreciation of what they are doing."

Challenges

- Faculty opt-in for the professional development was low
- Self-selection bias
- Adjuncts unskilled in exchanging observation feedback with peers
- Unsustainable practice without grant funds

Wood, B., Faulconer, E., & Chamberlain, D. (2024). *Lessons from professional development for remote STEM faculty*. [Manuscript under review]

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Evaluating the Col-CL Framework

An intervention was designed and implemented to promote Community of Inquiry and reduce extraneous cognitive load in asynchronous online discussions through assignment redesign and instructor professional development. The first step in evaluating this Framework was to determine if the efforts achieved the intended to the Col presences and cognitive load.

Social Presence

- Indirect measure: statistically **significant** increase (p-value=0.096).
- Direct measure: **significant** increase (43%).

Teaching Presence

- Indirect measure: No statistically significant difference (p-value 0.914).
- Direct measure: Decrease in teaching presence by 18%.

Cognitive Presence

- Indirect measure: Potential increase (p-value = 0.206).
- Direct measure: **Increase** in cognitive presence by 8%.

Cognitive Load

- Reduced frustration for understanding expectations, crafting an initial post, and integrating instructor feedback, suggesting **reduced extraneous load**
- Increased cognitive load in reading and replying to posts combined with increase in cognitive presence suggests **increased germane load**
- In Framework, more effort in replying to other students and less effort in replying to instructor, suggesting **increased student-to-student engagement**

Chamberlain, D., & Faulconer, E. (2024). *Engaging asynchronous discussions: Impact of an intervention to enhance community and improve learner outcomes*. [Manuscript in preparation]

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Evaluating the Col-CL Framework

Once the intended goal of the redesign and professional development on COI and cognitive load was confirmed, the impact of the Col-CL Framework on learner outcomes was evaluated.

Persistence

- Statistically significant decrease in W rate (-1.3%, p-value=0.0154).
Suggests Framework increased persistence.

Performance

- No statistical change in pass rate (-1%, p-value=0.2873).
- Mixed results for grade distribution shifts based on discipline.
- Suggests course redevelopments accounted for differences in grade distribution and not professional development intervention.

Challenges

- Lack of external circumstances data (notes from advisors after withdrawals)
- Incomplete persistence data prohibits us from statistically testing the above theoretical model of interactions

Chamberlain, D., & Faulconer, E. (2024). *Engaging asynchronous discussions: Impact of an intervention to enhance community and improve learner outcomes.* [Manuscript in preparation]

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Evaluating the Col-CL Framework STEM Attitudes

In addition to standard measures of impact, we also explored the impact of the intervention to improve asynchronous class discussions on learners' STEM attitudes. This study used a modification of the BRAINS survey. Prior to this study, relationship between Community of Inquiry, cognitive load, and STEM attitudes was not known. STEM attitudes correlate to STEM career interest, so a positive impact in this area can improve the health of the STEM career pipeline.

Chamberlain, D. & Faulconer, E. (2024). *STEM Attitudes in Asynchronous Online Discussions: Impact of an Intervention aimed at promoting community and reducing extraneous cognitive load.* [Manuscript in progress]

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Evaluating the Col-CL Framework STEM Attitudes

Takeaways

- SEM model validates the modified BRAINS survey from primary/secondary science to postsecondary STEM.
- Average percentage of positive responses for each attribute factor:
 - Attitude beliefs: 74%
 - Control beliefs: 78%
 - Normative beliefs: 52%
 - Intentions: 71%
 - Behavior: 69%
- Statistically significant increases in Normative Beliefs (p-value=0.0614), Control Beliefs (p-value=0.0522), and Intention (p-value=0.0882) in STEM after intervention.

Challenges

- Transient background factors such as mood and emotion affect attitude **in the moment**, which causes additional noise in modeling data.
- Data collected from two introductory-level STEM courses (Physics and Mathematics) may not be representative.
- Large number of latent factors reduces statistical measure of variance.

Chamberlain, D. & Faulconer, E. (2024). *STEM Attitudes in Asynchronous Online Discussions: Impact of an Intervention aimed at promoting community and reducing extraneous cognitive load.* [Manuscript in progress]

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Additional Dissemination Efforts

Code and Data Sets

https://github.com/Darryl-Chamberlain-Jr/Col_Python_Database_Analysis

Conference Presentations

Chamberlain Jr., D., McGuinness, P., Faulconer, E., & Wood, B. (2023, February 22-24). Using Trees to See a Forest: Leveraging Machine Learning to Classify Student Thinking [Poster presentation]. 25th Annual Conference on Research in Undergraduate Mathematics Education: SIGMAA on RUME, Omaha, NE.

Faulconer, E. (2023, March 22 - 25) *Community in the Online Science Classroom*. [Invited Lecture]. NSTA National Conference, Atlanta, GA, United States. <https://commons.erau.edu/publication/2026>

Faulconer, E., Chamberlain, D., & Wood, B. (2022, April) *Instructional efficiency in asynchronous online discussions*. Online Learning Consortium's Innovate, Dallas, TX, United States. <https://commons.erau.edu/publication/1998/>

Faulconer, E. (2022, January) *Cognitive load in asynchronous discussions in a fully online course*. Lilly Conference, San Diego, CA, United States. <https://commons.erau.edu/publication/1997/>

Strategic Dissemination

Faulconer, E., Chamberlain, D., Jr., & Wood, B. (2024). Community of Inquiry and Cognitive Load in Online STEM: Transferability Plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11203344>

Faulconer, E., Wood, B., & Chamberlain, D., Jr. (2024). Community of Inquiry and Cognitive Load NSF Program Outcomes Report. [URL Pending]

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Internal Stakeholder Communication

Wood, B., Chamberlain, D., & Faulconer, E. (2024, August). Worldwide Faculty Senate Briefing: *Gathering Nuanced Data for Understanding Student Withdrawals*. Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University. Daytona Beach, FL.

Wood, B., Chamberlain, D., & Faulconer, E. (2024, May). Worldwide Campus Dean Briefing: *Gathering Nuanced Data for Understanding Student Withdrawals*. Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University, online.

Wood, B., Faulconer, E., Chamberlain, D. (2024, May). *Gathering Nuanced Data for Understanding Student Withdrawals* [White Paper]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11094757>

Wood, B., Faulconer, E., & Chamberlain, D. (2024, February) *Investigating Community of Inquiry and Cognitive Load*. College of Arts & Sciences Brown Bag Research Lunch & Learn. Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University, online.
<https://commons.erau.edu/publication/2220/>

Faulconer, E. (2021, September). *My Brain is Full: Extraneous Cognitive Load in Asynchronous Discussions of an Online STEM Course*. College of Arts & Sciences Brown Bag Lunch & Learn. Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University, online. <http://works.bepress.com/emily-faulconer/102/>

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Internal Impacts

- Fourteen faculty received professional development in Community of Inquiry and Cognitive Load. Two of these faculty are full-time, and one is a recently retired full professor. The remaining eleven are contingent faculty.
- Nineteen full-time faculty, two adjuncts, the college Dean and one staff member attended the presentation on the withdrawal data collection.
- Students who have taken the redesigned class: 1392 in MATH 111 and 1517 in PHYS 102.
- Six Undergraduate researchers were actively involved in the research.

Broader Impacts

Advance Discovery and Promote Learning

- Robust SEM modeling demonstrated the Col-CL Framework:
 - reduced extraneous cognitive load and increased germane cognitive load (cognitive presence) through targeted interventions to course design and facilitation of asynchronous discussions by instructors
 - decreased withdrawal rate
 - Increased STEM attitudes (normative beliefs, control beliefs, intention)
- Validated modified BRAINS survey used in new context (postsecondary STEM)
- Validated NASA TLX survey used in new context (asynchronous online discussions)

Benefit to Society

- Col-CL Framework was validated as a tool for improving online learning, with potential for adoption and adaptation to other disciplines
- Stronger understanding of relationships between community of inquiry and cognitive load through robust modeling and empirical evidence
- Disseminated open-source Python scripts that interface with Canvas through API to collect discussion posts

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Next Steps

- **Scalability and Sustainability**

With the evidence of the efficacy of the Col-CL Framework, we will aim to transfer knowledge and strategies developed from this project to other asynchronous online STEM courses internally and externally. To this end, we prepared a Transferability Plan. Future efforts will explore scalability and sustainability of the Col-CL Framework.

Falconer, E., Chamberlain, D., & Wood, B. (2024, May). Community of Inquiry and Cognitive Load in Online STEM: Transferability Plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11203344>

- **Faculty Mindset**

Explore how faculty beliefs about student learning influence their implementation of Col strategies, allowing for informed targeted professional development to foster growth mindset and optimize Col strategies for facilitating online STEM courses.

- **Shared Metacognition**

Metacognition is an important component of cognitive presence and can be regulated through teaching presence. Future work should investigate adding a shared metacognition dimension to cognitive presence ([Garrison, 2023](#)). Co-regulation of learning as a component within a Community of Inquiry warrants further empirical evidence.

- **Virtual Professional Development**

Faculty buy-in for the asynchronous online professional development associated with this project was low. The duration of impacts of PD also have concerns. We will investigate strategies to increase buy-in and improve the duration of impact of PD through asynchronous opportunities for faculty.

- **Generative AI**

Generative AI (genAI) is a disruptive technology in higher education that has impacts learner and instructor presences. Future work should explore how the use of genAI in engaging in asynchronous online discussions influences students' demonstrated levels of cognitive presence, perceived germane load, and metacognition.

